

**ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF BLACK AND GREEN TEA
EXTRACTS AGAINST MULTIDRUG RESISTANCE *SHIGELLA*
SONNEI AND *SHIGELLA FLEXNERI*: AN INTEGRATED
EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND COMPUTATIONAL APPROACH**

**Md. Eram Hosen¹, Faria Tasnim¹, Meherun Nesa¹, Md. Sojiur Rahman¹, Md. Faruk
Hasan² and Rashed Zaman^{1*}**

¹Department of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, University of Rajshahi, Rajshahi-6205, Bangladesh.

²Department of Microbiology, University of Rajshahi, Rajshahi-6205, Bangladesh.

Article Received on
19 Oct. 2021,

Revised on 09 Nov. 2021,
Accepted on 30 Nov. 2021

DOI: 10.20959/wjpps202112-20410

***Corresponding Author**

Dr. Rashed Zaman

Department of Genetic
Engineering and
Biotechnology, University
of Rajshahi, Rajshahi-6205,
Bangladesh.

ABSTRACT

Shigella spp. is well known for shigellosis in humans. Growing resistance pattern of *Shigella spp.* to different antibiotics is increasing global public health concerns. This study has been conducted to evaluate the antibiotics sensitivity of *Shigella sonnei* and *Shigella flexneri*, the antibacterial activity of methanol extract of black tea (BT) and green tea (GT), and the docking study was performed using 28 phytochemicals from *Camellia sinensis* with *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG (4BVU) as well as in silico drug-likeness and ADME properties were also studied. Both *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* exhibited diverse antibiotics resistance patterns. Interestingly, methanol extract of GT showed higher antibacterial activity than BT extract against both bacteria. In addition, the docking study exposed 50% phytochemicals from *Camellia sinensis* which have strong inhibitory activity against 4BVU compared to control ciprofloxacin with binding energy of more than -7.40 kcal/mol. The highest binding affinity -9.70 kcal/mol was found by theaflavin with 21 interacting amino acid residues from 4BVU. However, drug-likeness and ADME properties showed Lipinski's violation of our top binding ligand theaflavin, whereas 2nd and 3rd highest binding compounds theaflavic acid and theaflagallin showed violation with one parameter in H-bond donor. Therefore, present observation suggests *Camellia sinensis* may have the inhibitory activity against *S. sonnei* and

S. flexneri, and phytochemicals theaflavic acid and theaflagallin could be used as effective drug candidates against *Shigella spp.*

KEYWORDS: *Shigellosis*, *Camellia sinensis*, Antibacterial activity, *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG, Molecular docking.

INTRODUCTION

Shigella spp. including *Shigella flexneri*, *Shigella sonnei*, *Shigella boydii*, and *Shigella dysenteriae* causing shigellosis in humans are responsible for diarrheal disease, leading to cause 165 million infections and 600,000 deaths each year.^[1] Among these four species of *Shigella*, *S. sonnei* along with *S. flexneri* causes 90% of shigellosis.^[2] Shigellosis is associated with diarrhea, dysentery, impaired nutrition absorption, recurrent infection, growth retardation, bloodstream infection, rectal prolapse, hemolytic-uremic syndrome, toxic megacolon and dehydration.^[3,4] Due to promiscuous use of drugs *Shigella* species are growing resistant to commonly used antibiotics, increasing the global health concern around the world. Resistance patterns of *Shigella spp.* are influenced by geographic location. Over the past few years, *Shigella* strains have gradually become resistant to different antibiotics such as ampicillin, nalidixic, chloramphenicol, tetracycline, ciprofloxacin, fluoroquinolones and ceftriaxone.^[5] It is high time to create new effective drugs to treat shigellosis but synthetic drugs may have side effects including kidney problem, blood disorder and abnormal blood clotting and most importantly weakening the body's immune system.^[6] Now people are interested in moving forward to use medicinal plants to treat infectious diseases as well as researchers are emphasizing to develop of new, secure and fecund drugs from plants against multidrug resistant pathogenic bacteria.

Tea (*Camellia sinensis*) belonging to the family of Theaceae is the most widely consumed beverage after water. There are two main types of tea including black tea (fermented) and green tea (non-fermented). Several studies reported that leaves from *Camellia sinensis* has anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antiviral, antioxidant, cholesterol lowering activity due to its wide range of phytochemicals.^[7,8] It is also used to treat skin disorders, asthma, mental ailments, arthritis and cardiovascular diseases.^[9]

Black tea contains more phytochemicals over green tea including catechin, theanine, caffeic acid, chlorogenic acid, theaflavic acid, theaflagallins, and neotheaflavate-3-O-gallate which

are accountable for anticlotting, anti-hyaluronidase, antidiarrheal, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, antimicrobials, and gastric ulcer healing activity.^[10-14]

Green tea consists of four main types of catechins including epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG), epigallocatechin, epicatechin-3-gallate and epicatechin, which have been reported to inhibit several varieties of pathogenic bacterial growth especially *Shigella spp.*, also effective against hepatitis, HIV and influenza viruses.^[8,15,16] Using plant phytochemicals with known antimicrobials properties can be of great implication in therapeutic treatments as well as drug discovery.^[17] Several in silico studies reported that phytochemicals from *Camellia sinensis* have inhibitory activity against some bacterial proteins.^[18,19]

Type III secretion is important for pathogenic bacteria to inject effector proteins for infection in human or host cells. OspG, a *Shigella* effector kinase plays vital role in promoting invasion and colonization, resulting to suppress host inflammatory response and trigger apoptosis in macrophages.^[20] OspG contains 211 amino acid residues among these 38 amino acid residues are present in the active site and making complex binding with ubiquitylated E2s, including UbcH5, interfering with activation of the NF- κ B pathway that involves UbcH5.^[21] Virtual screening of phytocompounds from *Camellia sinensis* might be a possible way to find out the potential antimicrobial agents against *Shigella spp.*

Plants have always been an exuberant source of phytochemicals with immense ethnopharmacology activity and used as conventional medical treatment for thousands of years. Our present investigation aimed to assess the drug sensitivity of *Shigella spp.* as well as the antibacterial activity of *Camellia sinensis* (black and green tea) leaf extract against multidrug resistance *Shigella spp.* In addition, we also investigated the binding affinity of *Camellia sinensis* phytochemicals with *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG and in silico drug-likeness and ADME properties of the phytochemicals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Materials

Two types of tea (*Camellia sinensis*) including BT and GT were selected for this experiment. Fresh, disease-free BT leaves were collected from Bangladesh Tea Research Institute (BTRI), Sylhet, Bangladesh and commercial GT was purchased from the local market.

Preparation of Extract

BT leaves were washed properly with distilled water to remove dirt, cut into small pieces, and air-dried for seven days. The dried leaves of BT and purchased GT were ground separately into a fine powder using a grinding machine. 50 g powdered of each sample were extracted with 150 ml of 100% methanol to produce a crude extract containing a wide range of active compounds and allowed to macerate on an orbital shaker for continuous shaking at 180 rpm for 48h. The respective extracts were first filtered with Markin cloth and then Whatman No.1 filter paper. The filtrates were evaporated and dried at 40 °C using a rotatory evaporator to yield a dense residue. Eventually, completely evaporated extract yields were weighed and stored in small bottles in the refrigerator at 4 °C.

Test Microorganism

Two strains of clinically important bacteria *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* were used for our present antibacterial investigation. These bacteria were obtained from International Central for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh (ICDDR, B).

Antibiotic Sensitivity Testing

Resistance patterns of the *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* isolates against various antibiotic drugs were determined by Bauer et al. (1966)^[22] with some modification of the disc diffusion method. In this current study, a total of 16 different antibiotics including penicillin-G (10 µg), cefixime (5 µg), azithromycin (15 µg), ampicillin (25 µg), gentamicin (10 µg), cephotoxime (30 µg), ofloxacin (5 µg), cefuroxime (30 µg), ciprofloxacin (5 µg), rifampicin (5 µg), streptomycin (10 µg), sulfonamid (300 µg), oxytetracycline (30 µg), nalidixic acid (30 µg), doxycycline (30 µg), and tobramycin (10 µg) were selected to observe the resistance patterns against *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri*. The bacteria were grown overnight in a nutrient broth at 37°C in a shaker with 180 rpm. Then overnight cultured of bacterial suspension (1×10^6 CFU/ml) were transferred and gently spread on the nutrient agar plate, and antibiotic discs were placed on the plate carefully. After 24h of incubation, clear zones indicated inhibition of the growth of the bacteria. The zone of inhibition was measured with the help of a millimeter (mm) scale.

Determination of Antibacterial Activity

Antibacterial activity of methanol leaf extract of BT and GT against *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* was determined by moderate disc diffusion method according to Carson et al.^[23] Five different concentrations of BT and GT of 50 µg/disc, 100 µg/disc, 150 µg/disc, 200 µg/disc

and 250 µg/disc were used for the antibacterial assay. Five mm in diameter filter paper discs were used for this experiment. The antibacterial activity was determined by measuring the zone of inhibition around the wells. The zone of inhibition was measured with the help of a millimeter (mm) scale.

Selection of *Camellia sinensis* Phytochemicals and Ligand Preparation

A total of 28 phytochemicals in *Camellia sinensis* and ciprofloxacin as positive control had been selected from different literature studies. The 2D structure images and sdf files of each phytochemical were downloaded from the PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>).^[24] The ligands were optimized and converted into pdb format with the help of Avogadro.^[25] With the intention of further simplify the analysis, ligands were first optimized and converted to pdbqt format using the PyRx virtual screening tool.^[26] All of these compounds were subjected to molecular docking against *Shigella* effectors protein kinase OspG (PDB Entry 4BVU). The name of the isolated compounds, their PubChem CID and references are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Phytochemicals of *Camellia sinensis* and control drug for in silico study.

Phytochemicals	PubChem CID	References
Caffeine	2519	
Epicatechin gallate	107905	
Epigallocatechin_gallate	65064	
Epicatechin	72276	[27]
Neochlorogenic_acid	5280633	
3-O-Caffeoylquinic acid	1794427	
Kaempferol-3-glucoside	5282102	
Gallic acid	370	
Caffeic_acid	689043	
Quercetin	5280343	
Ellagic acid	5281855	[28]
Eugenol	3314	
Catechin	9064	
Hesperetin	72281	
Theaflavic acid	135452274	[10]
Theaflagallin	73818214	
Hydroxycaffeic acid	11063337	
L-Threonate	21145021	[29]
Vanilic acid	8468	
Spinacetin 3-glucoside	44259790	
Gallocatechin	9882981	
Catechin gallate	6419835	[30]
Theaflavin	135403798	

5-galloylquinic acid	14520970	[31]
Theobromine	5429	
Kaempferol 3-rutinoside	5318767	
Theophylline	2153	[32]
Anthocyanin	145858	
Control (Ciprofloxacin)	2764	

Collection and Preparation of Protein

In our present investigation *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG (PDB entry 4BVU) was selected for docking. X-ray crystallography 3D structure of OspG/UbcH5c~Ub complex were downloaded from RCSB-PDB database (<https://www.rcsb.org/>).^[20] The protein structure was processed by removing the water and other hetatams using Discovery Studio 2021.^[33] Subsequently, energy minimization of protein was performed using GROMOS96 43B1 parameters by SwissPDB viewer.^[34] Polar hydrogens were added and finally converted into pdbqt file format using PyRx tool.

Active Site Identification

Active site amino acid residues in 4BVU was identified using an online server named CastP (<http://sts.bioe.uic.edu/castp/index.html?2pk9>).^[35]

Compound Screening Using PyRx Program

Following the phytochemicals and protein were prepared, molecular screening was carried out using PyRx software by autodock wizard as the engine for docking.^[26] The grid parameters were set on active site pocket of 4BVU, as x, y, z size and center coordinates are x= -74.667, y= 16.966, z= -7.811 and dimensions (angstrom) were x= 25.749, y= 31.638, z= 30.312. After docking, the highest binding energy (most negative) was considered as the ligands with maximum binding affinity. Visual analysis of the docking site was performed using Discovery Studio.^[33]

Analysis of Drug-likeness and ADME Properties

Drug-likeness properties of 28 phytochemicals were studied using SwissADME (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>)^[36] and PubChem database (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>). The drug-likeness properties of selected drugs were evaluated based on Lipinski's rule.^[37] Similarly, the absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) properties of drugs were predicted using SwissADME.

RESULTS

Antibiotic Sensitivity Assay

Antibiotic sensitivity assay of *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* showed different sensitivity patterns against the tested antibiotics with the zone of inhibition ranging from 0.00 ± 0.00 mm to 37.33 ± 0.33 mm (Figure 1).

Our current study found that *S. sonnei* showed fully resistance against four antibiotic drugs including cefixime (5 µg/disc), cephotaxime (30 µg/disc), sulfonamid (300 µg/disc), and oxytetracycline (30 µg/disc). In *S. sonnei*, the highest antibacterial activity was found by ofloxacin (5 µg/disc) with zone of inhibition of 37.33 ± 0.33 mm. In addition, *S. sonnei* showed slightly resistance against doxycycline (30 µg/disc) with zone of inhibition of 12.00 ± 0.00 mm (Figure 1(A)).

The present investigation also found that antibiotic resistance pattern of *S. flexneri* exhibited 100% resistance against six different antibiotics that consist of penicillin-G (10 µg/disc), cefixime (5 µg/disc), azithromycin (15 µg/disc), streptomycin (10 µg/disc), oxytetracycline (30 µg/disc) and nalidixic acid (30 µg/disc). Moreover, Figure 2(B) depicted that *S. flexneri* also have a significant resistance pattern against rifampicin (5 µg/disc), ampicillin (25 µg/disc), doxycyclin (30 µg/disc), cefuroxime (30 µg/disc) and sulfonamid (300 µg/disc) with zone of inhibition 7.17 ± 0.16 mm, 7.33 ± 0.33 mm, 8.33 ± 0.16 mm, 8.83 ± 0.16 mm and 9.17 ± 0.16 mm correspondingly. The highest antibacterial activity against *S. flexneri* was found by ciprofloxacin (5 µg/disc) with zone of inhibition 18.87 ± 0.16 mm (Figure 1(B)).

Figure 1: Antibiotic resistance patterns of *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* against 16 different antibiotic drugs; Zone of inhibition (mm) of *S. sonnei* (A); and *S. flexneri* (B). Values are represented by (mean \pm SE) of three biological replicates.

Determination of Antibacterial Activity

Methanol extract of BT and GT exposed diverse ranges of antibacterial activity against *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* with zone of inhibition ranging from 6.83 ± 0.44 mm to 20.83 ± 0.44 mm at five different concentrations viz. 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ (Figure 2).

In BT extract, significant growth inhibiting activity was found against both *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* at different concentrations (Figure 2(A) and 1(B)). Methanol extract of BT exhibited highest antibacterial activity against *S. sonnei* with zone of inhibition 16.89 ± 0.16 mm at the concentration of 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ shown in Figure 2(A). At 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ concentration, BT extract showed the lowest antibacterial activity against *S. flexneri* with zone of inhibition 6.83 ± 0.44 mm (Figure 2(B)). The current result asserted that BT extract at same concentration showed better growth inhibiting activity against *S. sonne* than *S. flexneri* (Figure 2(A) and (B)).

Figure 2: Antibacterial activity of methanol leaf extract of BT and GT against *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* and their zone of inhibition (mm) at five different concentrations viz. 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$; zone of inhibition of BT against *S. sonnei* (A); BT against *S. flexneri* (B); GT against *S. sonnei* (C); GT against *S. flexneri* (D). Data are represented by (mean \pm SE) of three biological replicates.

Antibacterial activity assay of GT extract exposed strong growth inhibiting activity against *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* at different concentrations. Figures 2(C) and 2(D) depicted *S. sonnei* showed better antibacterial activities over *S. flexneri* at every concentration after the treatment with GT extract. The maximum and minimum antibacterial activity was recorded against *S. sonnei* with zone of inhibition 20.83 ± 0.44 mm and 8.5 ± 0.28 mm at the concentration of 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ respectively.

Present antibacterial study of BT and GT exposed that, highest antibacterial activity was found in GT against *S. sonnei* with zone of inhibition 20.83 ± 0.44 mm at the concentration of 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$. In contrast, BT at 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ concentration showed the lowest activity against *S. flexneri* with zone of inhibition 6.83 ± 0.44 mm (Figure 2). Moreover, GT extract exhibited better antibacterial activity than BT extract against both *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* at every concentration that were used in this experiment.

Selection of *Camellia sinensis* Phytochemicals and target protein

We have investigated 28 phytochemicals from the *Camellia sinensis* plant against *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG (PDB entry 4BVU). Our current investigation found that all of these compounds have inhibitory activity against 4BVU protein.

Resembling other pathogenic bacteria, *Shigella ssp.* promotes invasion and colonization in the host by introducing their effector kinase protein OspG and playing a critical role to suppress the host inflammatory response. In our current study, we selected OspG protein (PDB entry 4BVU) as a target which has been reported to form a complex with host E2 ubiquitin-conjugating enzymes. After modifying these proteins, they were subjected to molecular docking.

Active-site Identification

Thirty-eight amino acids were found in the binding pocket of 4BVU protein. The active site amino acid residues of 4BVU are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Binding site residues of *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG

Target Protein	Binding site residues
<i>Shigella</i> effector protein kinase OspG (PDB entry 4BVU)	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, SER37, THR38, ALA39, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, TYR55, ASP56, ILE58, ASN60, ILE65, MET68, GLN71, GLU72, LEU75, PHE76, LEU96, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, GLY103, PRO105, SER107, ASP108, ASP138, GLY142, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, ASN157, PHE158, ARG159, ASN160, ARG179

Compound Screening Using PyRx Program

In our present study, all 28 phytochemicals from *Camellia sinensis* were analyzed for the binding affinity against *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG. Table 3 showed the binding energies (kcal/mol), the number of hydrogen bonds and the interacting amino acid residues of 28 phytocompounds with 4BVU. A molecular docking study had found the inhibitory activity of *Camellia sinensis* compounds against 4BVU protein with binding energy ranging from -4.70 to -9.70 kcal/mol. About 50% (14 out of 28) of the *Camellia sinensis* compounds were found to have better binding affinity compared to the control ciprofloxacin with binding energy of more than -7.40 kcal/mol against 4BVU. The average binding energy was found -7.09 kcal/mol, where 18 compounds showed strong binding affinity against 4BVU than average binding energy. Theaflavin showed the highest binding affinity with -9.70kcal/mol, where L-Threonate exhibited the lowest binding affinity with -4.70 kcal/mol to 4BVU protein.

Table 3: Docking results of 28 ligands from *Camellia sinensis* phytochemicals and control (ciprofloxacin) against *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG.

Ligands	Binding energy kcal/mol	Number of hydrogen bonds	Interacting amino acid residues with 4BVU
Caffeine	-5.40	2	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ILE41, LYS53, MET98, ILE156, ASP157
Epicatechingallate	-8.00	6	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, GLU72, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, PRO102, GLY103, PRO105, GLY142, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Epigallocatechin_gallate	-8.20	3	ILE33, GLY34, GLY36, ALA39, GLN35, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, GLU72, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, GLY103, PRO105, GLY142, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Epicatechin	-7.30	2	ILE33, GLY34, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, GLU72, MET98, ARG100, GLY103, THR104, PRO105, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Neochlorogenic_acid	-7.50	4	ILE33, GLN35, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, PRO102, GLY103, THR104, PRO105, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Chlorogenic_acid	-8.20	5	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, THR38, ALA39, GLU40, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, GLY103, THR104, PRO105, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Kaempferol-3-glucoside	-7.50	4	GLY34, GLN35, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, PRO105, SER107, ASP108, ASP138, ASN140, GLY142, ASN143, ILE156, ASP157
Gallic acid	-5.30	3	GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, THR38, ALA39, ILE41, LYS53, MET98, ILE156, ASP157
Caffeic_acid	-6.00	1	ILE33, IE41, LEU51, LYS53, GLU72, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157, PHE158
Quercetin	-7.70	3	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, LEU145, ASP157, ILE156
Ellagic acid	-7.90	1	ASP157, ASN143, GLY36, GLN35, ILE41, GLY34, ILE33, LEU145, ARG100, LEU51, VAL 101, LEU99, PHE76, ILE156, MET98, LYS53
Eugenol	-5.40	1	GLY34, GLN35, ALA39, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, VAL101, ILE156, LEU145, ASP157

Catechin	-7.40	2	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, GLY103, THR104, PRO105, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Hesperetin	-7.80	2	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Theaflavic acid	-8.70	3	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, THR38, ALA39, ILE41, LEU51, GLY103, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, THR104, PRO105, LEU145, LYS53, GLU72, ASN143, ILE156, ASP157
Theaflagallin	-8.60	5	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, SER37, ALA39, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, THR104, ARG100, VAL101, PRO102, GLY103, PRO105, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Hydroxycaffeic acid	-5.80	3	ILE33, GLY34, GLY36, THR38, ALA39, GLU40, ILE41, LYS53, MET98, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
L-Threonate	-4.70	5	GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, SER37, THR38, ALA39, GLU40, ILE41, LYS53, ASN143, ILE156, ASP157
Vanilic acid	-5.10	3	GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, THR38, ALA39, ILE41, LYS53, MET98, ILE156, ASP157
Spinacetin-3-glucoside	-7.90	2	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, ALA39, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, GLY103, THR 104, PRO105, SER107, ASP108, GLY142, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Gallocatechin	-7.20	0	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, GLY103, THR104, PRO105, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Catechingallate	-8.20	6	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, GLU72, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, PRO102, GLY103, THR104, PRO105, GLY142, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Theaflavin	-9.70	2	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, PRO102, GLY103, THR104, PRO105, SER107, ASP108, GLY142, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
5-galloylquinic acid	-7.00	2	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ALA39, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, GLY103, PRO105, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Theobromine	-5.20	0	THR38, LYS53, TYR55, MET68, GLU72, ASP138, ASP157, PHE158, ARG159
Kaempferol-3-	-8.20	3	GLY34, GLY36, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, PRO105, SER107, ASP108,

rutinoside			ASP108, ASP138, ASN140, THR141, GLY142, ASN143, ILE156, ASP157, ASP186
Theophylline	-5.20	2	GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ALA39, ILE41, LYS53, MET98, ILE156, ASP157
Anthocyanin	-7.30	0	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, ILE41, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157
Control (Ciprofloxacin)	-7.40	1	ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ALA39, THR38, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, GLY103, PRO105, LEU145, ILE156, ASP157

Theaflavin exhibited the best docking score -9.70 kcal/mol with 4BVU and 21 amino acid residues of 4BVU such as ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, PRO102, GLY103, THR104, PRO105, SER107, ASP108, GLY142, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156 and ASP157 were found to make interaction with the ligand. Out of 38 active side amino acid residues, 19 residues showed interaction with the ligand theaflavin. Two H-bonds were formed between ligand theaflavin and GLN35 and ARG100 amino acids of 4BVU. In addition, out of 21 ligands-interacting bonds, two were pi-sigma, and the remaining 17 were van der Waals bond (Figure 3(A) and 3(B)). The hydrophobicity and H-bond donor or acceptor property are presented in Figures 3(C) and 3(D) respectively.

Figure 3: Binding interaction of *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG (4BVU) with theaflavin. Three-dimensional display of ligand-4BVU protein interaction and surface view of theaflavin (A); Two-dimensional display of ligand-4BVU protein interaction (B); hydrophobicity (C) and H-bond property of binding pocket (D).

Another compound theaflavic acid, emerged docking score -8.70 kcal/mol with target protein 4BVU. Twenty amino acid residues of 4BVU protein for instance ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, THR38, ALA39, ILE41, LEU51, GLY103, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, THR104, PRO105, LEU145, LYS53, GLU72, ASN143, ILE156 and ASP157 were found making interaction with ligands of theaflavic acid. Among these interacting residues, 19 active site residues were found to make interact with ligand. Three H-bonds were found between GLN35, GLY103 and ASP157 amino acid residues of 4BVU and ligand (Figure 4(A) and

4(B)). The hydrophobicity and H-bond donor or acceptor property are presented in Figures 4(C) and 4(D).

Figure 4: Binding interaction of *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG (4BVU) protein with theaflavic acid. Three-dimensional display of ligand-4BVU protein interaction and surface view of theaflavic acid (A); Two-dimensional display of ligand-4BVU protein interaction (B); hydrophobicity (C) and H-bond property of binding pocket (D).

In theaflagallin, five H-bond were revealed between GLN35, LYS53, ARG100, VAL101 and GLY103 amino acid residue of 4BVU and ligand. ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, SER37, ALA39, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, THR104, ARG100, VAL101, PRO102, GLY103, PRO105, ASN143, LEU145, ILE156, and ASP157 were the amino acid residues of 4BVU making interaction with ligand theaflagallin with docking score of -8.60 kcal/mol, where 18 residues were presented in the active site (Figure 5(A) and 5(B)). The hydrophobicity and H-bond donor or acceptor property are presented in Figures 5(C) and 5(D).

Molecular docking study between control drug ciprofloxacin and 4BVU protein exposed binding energy of -7.40 kcal/mol. Two-dimensional display of protein ligand interaction showed 17 amino acid residues of 4BVU such as ILE33, GLY34, GLN35, GLY36, ALA39, THR38, ILE41, LEU51, LYS53, MET98, ARG100, VAL101, GLY103, PRO105, LEU145, ILE156 and ASP157 were making interaction with ciprofloxacin. Additionally, one H-bond was found between LYS53 amino acid residue of 4BVU and ciprofloxacin. Moreover, all of these amino acid residues were present in the active site (Figure 6(A) and 6(B)). The hydrophobicity and H-bond donor or acceptor property are shown in Figure 6(C) and 6(D).

Figure 5: Binding interaction of *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG (4BVU) protein with theaflagallin. Three-dimensional display of ligand-4BVU protein interaction and surface view of theaflagallin (A); Two-dimensional display of ligand-4BVU protein interaction (B); hydrophobicity (C) and H-bond property of binding pocket (D).

Figure 6: Binding interaction of *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG (4BVU) protein with control (ciprofloxacin). Three-dimensional display of ligand-4BVU protein interaction and surface view of ciprofloxacin (A); Two-dimensional display of ligand-4BVU protein interaction (B); hydrophobicity (C) and H-bond property of binding pocket (D).

Analysis of Drug-likeness and ADME Properties

To predict the drug-likeness of a compound, it is imperative to analyze the absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) profile of this compound. Lipinski's rule of five is a major criterion to evaluate drug likeliness properties. According to Lipinski's rule, a compound may be considered a drug-likeness if the compound maintains the following conditions (a) a molecular weight ≤ 500 Da, (b) H-bond donor ≤ 5 , (c) H-bond acceptor ≤ 10 , (d) LogP value ≤ 5 and (e) Lipinski's violation ≤ 3 . Table 4 showed that ADME study of our investigated 28 compounds where 15 compounds successfully passed the ADME test with all of these parameters, eight compounds violated the Lipinski's low with one parameter and the remaining four compounds violated the Lipinski's rule with two or more parameters. Our best binding compound theaflavin showed violation in Lipinski's rules, whereas the 2nd and 3rd highest binding compounds theaflavic acid and theaflagallin showed violation with one parameter in H-bond donor.

Table 4: Drug-likeness properties of *Camellia sinensis* phytochemicals.

Phytochemicals	Molecular formula	MW (g/mol)	HBD ≤ 5	HBA ≤ 10	LogP ≤ 5	Lipinski's
Caffeine	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂	194.19	0.00	3.00	1.79	Yes; 0 violation
Epicatechin gallate	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₁₀	442.37	7.00	10.00	1.44	Yes; 1 violation
Epigallocatechin_gallate	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₁₁	458.37	8.00	11.00	1.87	No; 2 violations
Epicatechin	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆	290.27	5.00	6.00	1.47	Yes; 0 violation
Neochlorogenic_acid	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₉	354.31	6.00	9.00	0.56	Yes; 1 violation
3-O-Caffeoylquinic acid	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₉	354.31	6.00	9.00	0.96	Yes; 1 violation
Kaempferol-3-glucoside	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₁	448.38	7.00	11.00	0.53	No; 2 violations
Gallic acid	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅	170.12	4.00	5.00	0.21	Yes; 0 violation
Caffeic_acid	C ₉ H ₈ O ₄	180.16	3.00	4.00	0.97	Yes; 0 violation
Quercetin	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇	302.241	5.00	7.00	1.63	Yes; 0 violation
Ellagic acid	C ₁₄ H ₆ O ₈	302.19	4.00	8.00	0.79	Yes; 0 violation
Eugenol	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂	164.20	1.00	2.00	2.37	Yes; 0 violation
Cianidanol (Catechin)	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆	290.27	5.00	6.00	1.47	Yes; 0 violation
Hesperetin	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₆	302.28	3.00	6.00	2.24	Yes; 0 violation
Theaflavic acid	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	428.35	7.00	10.00	0.97	Yes; 1 violation
Theaflagallin	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₉	400.34	7.00	9.00	1.29	Yes; 1 violation
Hydroxycaffeic acid	C ₉ H ₈ O ₅	196.16	4.00	5.00	0.93	Yes; 0 violation
L-Threonate	C ₄ H ₇ O ₅	135.10	3.00	5.00	0.06	Yes; 0 violation
Vanilic acid	C ₈ H ₈ O ₄	168.15	2.00	4.00	1.4	Yes; 0 violation
Spinacetin-3-glucoside	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₁₃	508.43	7.00	13.00	2.67	No; 3 violations
Gallocatechin	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₇	306.27	6.00	7.00	0.98	Yes; 1 violation
Catechin gallate	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₁₀	442.37	7.00	10.00	1.44	Yes; 1 violation
Theaflavin	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₁₂	564.49	9.00	12.00	1.84	No; 3 violations
5-galloylquinic acid	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₁₀	344.27	7.00	10.00	-0.74	Yes; 1 violation
Theobromine	C ₇ H ₈ N ₄ O ₂	180.16	1.00	3.00	1.22	Yes; 0 violation

Kaempferol-3-rutinoside	C27H30O15	594.52	9.00	15.00	2.79	No; 3 violations
Theophylline	C7H8N4O2	180.16	1.00	3.00	0.53	No; 1 violations
Anthocyanin	C15H11O	207.25	0.00	1.00	-0.76	Yes; 0 violation

DISCUSSION

Shigellosis costs millions of lives during the last few decades and antibiotic is the only way to treat it. But the mounting resistance of *Shigella spp.* against multiple antibiotic drugs is increasing the concerns worldwide. These current situations awakened researchers to develop new drugs from plants. According to the current study, *S. sonnei* showed 100% resistance against four antibiotic drugs such as cefixime (5 µg/disc), cephotaxime (30 µg/disc), sulfonamid (300 µg/disc) and oxytetracycline (30 µg/disc) (Figure 1(A)). Likewise, *S. flexneri* exhibited fully resistance against six antibiotic drugs such as penicillin-G (10 µg/disc), cefixime (5 µg/disc), azithromycin (15 µg/disc), streptomycin (10 µg/disc), oxytetracycline (30 µg/disc) and nalidixic Acid (30 µg/disc) (Figure 1(B)).

R. Nath et al. (2013) described *S. flexneri* had grown resistance activity to ofloxacin, nalidixic acid, azithromycin, gentamicin, ciprofloxacin and cefotaxime with 93.5%, 90.3%, 62.9%, 77.4%, 88.7% and 95.1% isolates respectively.^[38] Another study showed, both *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* were resistant to ampicillin, tetracyclin, streptomycin, sulfamethoxazole, nalidixic acid, torbramcyin and cefotaxime.^[39] In addition, our present findings demonstrated *S. flexneri* had a higher multiple drug resistances rate than *S. sonnei*. Kuo, C. Y et al. (2008) asserted *S. flexneri* had a higher drug resistance rate over *S. sonnei* with 74% and 23% respectively.^[40] Aforementioned findings of *Shigella spp.* multiple drug resistances supported our current investigation. There are various mechanisms involved in *Shigella spp.* such as ejection of drugs by active efflux pumps, lessening cellular permeability, overexpression of drug modifying, deactivating enzyme and chromosomal target site mutation that are facilitated *Shigella spp.* to resistance against multiple drugs.^[41] Therefore, it is time to continue monitoring the drug sensitivity pattern of *Shigella spp.* and ascertain an effective way to develop new secure drugs.

Our present study as well found the significant antibacterial activity of both BT and GT extract against *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* at five different concentrations viz. 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 µg/disc (Figure 4). Methanol leaf of BT and GT extract exhibited highest antibacterial activity against *S. sonnei* with the zone of inhibition 16.89±0.16 mm and 20.83±0.44 respectively at the concentration of 250 µg/disc Figure 4(A) and 4(C). Several

studies reported that *Camellia sinensis* leaf extract has the strong antibacterial activity.^[7,8] Moreover, GT extract showed better antibacterial activity than BT extract against both *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri*. Farooqui et al. (2015) indicated green tea extract has higher antibacterial activity against multidrug resistance bacteria.^[42]

In the present study, BT extract exhibited antibacterial activity against gram negative *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* with zone of inhibition ranging 7.83 ± 0.44 mm to 16.83 ± 0.16 mm and 6.83 ± 0.44 mm to 15.83 ± 0.16 mm respectively. Similarly, GT extract also showed outstanding antibacterial activity against *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* ranging 8.5 ± 0.28 mm to 20.83 ± 0.44 mm and 10.16 ± 0.44 to 19.33 ± 0.33 mm respectively. Patil M et al. (2016) reported that BT extract has antibacterial activity against gram negative bacteria with zone of inhibition ranging 12.33 ± 0.58 mm to 17.33 ± 0.58 mm.^[7] Previous studies showed that *Camellia sinensis* had antibacterial activity against multiple drug resistances pathogens such as *S. dysenteriae*, *S. flexneri* and *Salmonella typhi*.^[42,43] R.P. Tiwari et al. (2005) mentioned GT has antibacterial activity against *S. dysenteriae*.^[44] Tea catechins mainly epigallocatechin (EGC) and epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG) exhibited strong antimicrobial activity by binding the ATP site of DNA gyrase b subunit of bacteria that inhibit its enzymatic activity, and the catechins polyphenol also damages the bacterial cell membrane.^[45] Hence, *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* were resistant to multiple drugs, therefore our findings of antibacterial activity of BT and GT extract against *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri* could play significant roles to develop effective drug from tea plant.

Interestingly, our current investigation also evaluated the inhibitory activity of 28 phytochemicals from *Camellia sinensis* against *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG and the molecular docking study showed 14 out of 28 phytochemicals have a strong binding affinity with 4BVU compared to control ciprofloxacin with binding energy of more than -7.40 kcal/mol Table 2. The highest docking score -9.70 kcal/mol was found against 4BVU by theaflavin with 19 interacting residues of 4bvuv active site indicating *Camellia sinensis* leaf extract have strong antibacterial activity against *Shigella spp.* A previous study reported that catechins from *Camellia sinensis* have strong binding affinity with bacterial protein.^[46] In addition, epicatechin, catechingallate, galocatechin, epicatechingallate and epigallocatechingallate inhibit 4BVU with docking scores -7.30, -8.20, -7.20, -8.0 and -8.20 kcal/mol respectively. Helena Gradis et al. (2007) and H Fikrika et al. (2016) revealed antibacterial activity of epicatechingallate (ECG), epigallocatechingallate (EGCG),

epicatechin, gallic acid and epigallocatechin by in silico study.^[47,48] Similarly our current study found binding affinity -7.70 kcal/mol of quercetin with 4BVU. Another in silico study reported quercetin from other plants inhibits *Shigella* extracellular protein A (SepA).^[49]

Our present in vitro and in silico study strongly recommended that BT and GT extract has outstanding inhibitory activity against *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri*. Since, drug resistance of *Shigella spp.* increases day by day, therefore, our study could play a significant role to develop an effective, new, and a secure drug against *Shigella spp.* More studies are required on *Shigella spp.* to understand the drug resistance mechanism of *Shigella spp.*

CONCLUSION

Our current study found both BT and GT extract have significant growth inhibitory activity against *S. sonnei* and *S. flexneri*. Additionally, in silico study also found several phytochemicals from *Camellia sinensis* have a strong inhibitory activity against *Shigella* effector protein kinase OspG. Since our best binding compound theaflavin showed Lipinski's violation, we proposed theaflavic acid and theaflavin compounds may be used as drug candidates to treat shigellosis.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to thank International Central for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh (ICDDR, B). The authors also want to thank all the contributors for being part of this research during a very demanding situation.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Brunette, G. W. (2017). *CDC Yellow Book 2018: health information for international travel*. Oxford University Press.
2. Medscape "Shigellosis Clinical". Available online: <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/182767-clinical> (accessed on 20 Aug 2021).
3. Mayo Clinic Staff "Shigella Infection". Available online: <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/shigella/symptoms-causes/syc-20377529> (accessed on 20 Aug 2021).

4. Kouitcheu LB, Tamesse JL, Kouam J. The anti-shigellosis activity of the methanol extract of *Picralima nitida* on *Shigella dysenteriae* type I induced diarrhoea in rats. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2013; 13(1): 1-1.
5. Peirano G, Souza FD, Rodrigues DD. Frequency of serovars and antimicrobial resistance in *Shigella* spp. from Brazil. *Memorias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz*, 2006; 101: 245-50.
6. Rajan S, Thirunalasundari T, Jeeva S. Anti—enteric bacterial activity and phytochemical analysis of the seed kernel extract of *Mangifera indica* Linnaeus against *Shigella dysenteriae* (Shiga, corrig.) Castellani and Chalmers. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine*, 2011; 4(4): 294-300.
7. Patil MP, Patil KT, Ngabire D, Seo YB, Kim GD. Phytochemical, antioxidant and antibacterial activity of black tea (*Camellia sinensis*). *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*, 2016; 8(2): 341-6.
8. Araghizadeh A, Kohanteb J, Fani MM. Inhibitory activity of green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) extract on some clinically isolated cariogenic and periodontopathic bacteria. *Medical Principles and Practice*, 2013; 22(4): 368-72.
9. Sharangi AB. Medicinal and therapeutic potentialities of tea (*Camellia sinensis* L.)—A review. *Food research international*, 2009; 42(5-6): 529-35.
10. Singh BN, Prateeksha, Rawat AK, Bhagat RM, Singh BR. Black tea: Phytochemicals, cancer chemoprevention, and clinical studies. *Critical reviews in food science and nutrition*, 2017; 57(7): 1394-410.
11. Ratnasooriya WD, Fernando TS. Antidiarrhoeal activity of Sri Lankan dust grade black tea (*Camellia sinensis* L.) in mice. *Pharmacognosy magazine*, 2009; 5(18): 115.
12. Ratnasooriya WD, Fernando TS. Anti-inflammatory activity of Sri Lankan black tea (*Camellia sinensis* L.) in rats. *Pharmacognosy Research*, 2009; 1(1).
13. Ratnasooriya WD, Fernando TS. Gastric ulcer healing activity of Sri Lankan black tea (*Camellia sinensis* L.) in rats. *Pharmacognosy Magazine*, 2009; 5(19): 260.
14. Jayakody JR, Ratnasooriya W. Blood glucose level lowering activity of Sri Lankan black tea brew (*Camellia sinensis*) in rats. *Pharmacognosy Magazine*, 2008; 4(16): 341.
15. Wang YF, Shao SH, Xu P, Yang XQ, Qian LS. Catechin-enriched green tea extract as a safe and effective agent for antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory treatment. *African Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 2011; 5(12): 1452-61.
16. Fassina G, Buffa A, Benelli R, Varnier OE, Noonan DM, Albin A. Polyphenolic antioxidant (–)-epigallocatechin-3-gallate from green tea as a candidate anti-HIV agent. *Aids*, 2002; 16(6): 939-41.

17. Nascimento GG, Locatelli J, Freitas PC, Silva GL. Antibacterial activity of plant extracts and phytochemicals on antibiotic-resistant bacteria. *Brazilian journal of microbiology*, 2000; 31: 247-56.
18. Pradhan S, Dubey RC. GC–MS analysis and molecular docking of bioactive compounds of *Camellia sinensis* and *Camellia assamica*. *Archives of Microbiology*, 2021; 1-0.
19. Qais FA, Khan MS, Ahmad I. Broad-spectrum quorum sensing and biofilm inhibition by green tea against gram-negative pathogenic bacteria: Deciphering the role of phytochemicals through molecular modelling. *Microbial pathogenesis*, 2019; 126: 379-92.
20. Pruneda JN, Smith FD, Daurie A, Swaney DL, Villén J, Scott JD, Stadnyk AW, Le Trong I, Stenkamp RE, Klevit RE, Rohde JR. E2~ Ub conjugates regulate the kinase activity of *Shigella* effector OspG during pathogenesis. *The EMBO journal*, 2014; 33(5): 437-49.
21. Kim DW, Lenzen G, Page AL, Legrain P, Sansonetti PJ, Parsot C. The *Shigella flexneri* effector OspG interferes with innate immune responses by targeting ubiquitin-conjugating enzymes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 2005; 102(39): 14046-51.
22. Bauer AW. Antibiotic susceptibility testing by a standardized single disc method. *Am J clin pathol*, 1966; 45: 149-58.
23. Carson CF, Riley TV. Antimicrobial activity of the major components of the essential oil of *Melaleuca alternifolia*. *Journal of applied bacteriology*, 1995; 78(3): 264-9.
24. Kim S, Chen J, Cheng T, Gindulyte A, He J, He S, Li Q, Shoemaker BA, Thiessen PA, Yu B, Zaslavsky L. PubChem in 2021: new data content and improved web interfaces. *Nucleic acids research*, 2021; 49(D1): D1388-95.
25. Hanwell MD, Curtis DE, Lonie DC, Vandermeersch T, Zurek E, Hutchison GR. Avogadro: an advanced semantic chemical editor, visualization, and analysis platform. *Journal of cheminformatics*, 2012; 4(1): 1-7.
26. Dallakyan S, Olson AJ. Small-molecule library screening by docking with PyRx. *InChemical biology*. Humana Press, New York, NY., 2015; 243-250.
27. Barreira S, Moutinho C, Silva AM, Neves J, Seo EJ, Hegazy ME, Efferth T, Gomes LR. Phytochemical characterization and biological activities of green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) produced in the Azores, Portugal. *Phytomedicine Plus*, 2021; 1(1): 100001.
28. Samadi S, Fard FR. Phytochemical properties, antioxidant activity and mineral content (Fe, Zn and Cu) in Iranian produced black tea, green tea and roselle calyces. *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology*, 2020; 23: 101472.

29. Xiao X, Erukainure OL, Sanni O, Koorbanally NA, Islam MS. Phytochemical properties of black tea (*Camellia sinensis*) and rooibos tea (*Aspalathus linearis*); and their modulatory effects on key hyperglycaemic processes and oxidative stress. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 2020; 57(12): 4345-54.
30. Nune SK, Chanda N, Shukla R, Katti K, Kulkarni RR, Thilakavathy S, Mekapothula S, Kannan R, Katti KV. Green nanotechnology from tea: phytochemicals in tea as building blocks for production of biocompatible gold nanoparticles. *Journal of materials chemistry*, 2009; 19(19): 2912-20.
31. Kim Y, Goodner KL, Park JD, Choi J, Talcott ST. Changes in antioxidant phytochemicals and volatile composition of *Camellia sinensis* by oxidation during tea fermentation. *Food Chemistry*, 2011; 129(4): 1331-42.
32. Fernando W, Somaratne G, Goozee KG, Williams S, Singh H, Martins RN. Diabetes and Alzheimer's disease: can tea phytochemicals play a role in prevention?. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 2017; 59(2): 481-501.
33. BIOVIA (2021), DassaultSystemes, (BIOVIA Discovery Studio), (Versions: 21.1.0.0), San Diego: DassaultSystemes.
34. Guex N, Peitsch MC. SWISS-MODEL and the Swiss-Pdb Viewer: an environment for comparative protein modeling. *Electrophoresis*, 1997; 18(15): 2714-23.
35. Tian W, Chen C, Lei X, Zhao J, Liang J. CASTp 3.0: computed atlas of surface topography of proteins. *Nucleic acids research*, 2018; 46(W1): W363-7.
36. Daina A, Michielin O, Zoete V. SwissADME: a free web tool to evaluate pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness and medicinal chemistry friendliness of small molecules. *Scientific reports*, 2017; 7(1): 1-3.
37. Lajiness MS, Vieth M, Erickson J. Molecular properties that influence oral drug-like behavior. *Current opinion in drug discovery & development*, 2004; 7(4): 470-7.
38. Majid A, Rahman MU, Shah JA, Khan K, Ali MA, Zamin I, Ullah Z, Ibrar M, Zaman Q. In vitro antibacterial activity of *Camellia sinensis* leaf extracts to some selective pathogenic bacterial strains. *International Journal of Biosciences*, 2013; 3(9): 69-75.
39. Mirnejad R, Vahdati AR, Rashidiani J, Erfani M, Piranfar V. The antimicrobial effect of lactobacillus casei culture supernatant against multiple drug resistant clinical isolates of *Shigella sonnei* and *Shigella flexneri* in vitro. *Iranian Red Crescent Medical Journal*, 2013; 15(2): 122.
40. Kuo CY, Su LH, Perera J, Carlos C, Tan BH, Kumarasinghe G, So T, Van PH, Chongthaleong A, Song JH, Chiu CH. Antimicrobial susceptibility of *Shigella* isolates in

- eight Asian countries, 2001-2004. *Journal of Microbiology, Immunology, and Infection*, 2008; 41(2): 107-11.
41. Ranjbar R, Farahani A. Shigella: antibiotic-resistance mechanisms and new horizons for treatment. *Infection and drug resistance*, 2019; 12: 3137.
 42. Farooqui A, Khan A, Borghetto I, Kazmi SU, Rubino S, Paglietti B. Synergistic antimicrobial activity of *Camellia sinensis* and *Juglans regia* against multidrug-resistant bacteria. *PloS one*, 2015; 10(2): e0118431.
 43. Vijaya K, Ananthan S, Nalini R. Antibacterial effect of theaflavin, polyphenon 60 (*Camellia sinensis*) and *Euphorbia hirta* on *Shigella* spp.—a cell culture study. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 1995; 49(2): 115-8.
 44. Tiwari RP, Bharti SK, Kaur HD, Dikshit RP, Hoondal GS. Synergistic antimicrobial activity of tea & antibiotics. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 2005; 122(1): 80.
 45. Gopal J, Muthu M, Paul D, Kim DH, Chun S. Bactericidal activity of green tea extracts: the importance of catechin containing nano particles. *Scientific Reports*, 2016; 6(1): 1-4.
 46. Kumar D, Poornima M, Kushwaha RN, Won TJ, Ahn C, Kumar CG, Jang K, Shin DS. Antimicrobial and docking studies of (–)-catechin derivatives. *Journal of the Korean society for applied biological chemistry*, 2015; 58(4): 581-5.
 47. Gradišar H, Pristovšek P, Plaper A, Jerala R. Green tea catechins inhibit bacterial DNA gyrase by interaction with its ATP binding site. *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 2007; 50(2): 264-71.
 48. Fikrika H, Ambarsari L, Sumaryada T. Molecular docking studies of catechin and its derivatives as anti-bacterial inhibitor for glucosamine-6-phosphate synthase. *InIOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 2016; (31(1): 012009). IOP Publishing.
 49. Hirudkar JR, Parmar KM, Prasad RS, Sinha SK, Jogi MS, Itankar PR, Prasad SK. Quercetin a major biomarker of *Psidium guajava* L. inhibits SepA protease activity of *Shigella flexneri* in treatment of infectious diarrhoea. *Microbial pathogenesis*, 2020; 138: 103807.